

DEFENSIVE INFORMATION STRATEGIES IN PAK-IRAN RELATIONS: ENHANCING DIPLOMATIC STABILITY

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ABSTRACT

This research highlights the importance of defensive information strategies in promoting diplomatic stability while examining the complex dynamics of these tactics in Pakistan-Iran relations. It addresses a crucial information vacuum in the use and effects of these tactics in this context by examining how they affect diplomatic outcomes, public narratives, and the reduction of cross-border tensions. The strategic use of information warfare between Pakistan and Iran is still little understood, despite its increasing significance in influencing public opinion and diplomatic relations. Moreover, the study's primary objectives are to: (1) assess how information warfare affects public narratives and how that affects regional stability; (2) determine and analyze the key strategies that both countries use to sway public opinion; (3) examine how Pakistan and Iran use public diplomacy to influence narratives. This research further offers thorough insights into how well defensive information tactics promote diplomatic stability and regional security by combining strategic evaluation with empirical analysis. It enhances the broader debate on information warfare and its effects on international relations within the Pak-Iran geopolitical context by providing useful suggestions for policymakers to improve diplomatic ties and promote regional stability.

Keywords: defensive information strategies, diplomatic outcomes, regional stability, public narratives.

INTRODUCTION

Information strategy involves the purposeful and coordinated utilization of information and communication channels to accomplish specific goals within a broader strategic context. This encompasses the planning, distribution, and oversight of information in ways that influence perceptions, shape public opinion, and further the interests of individuals, groups, or states. It includes various tactics such as media campaigns, propaganda efforts, psychological operations,

and the manipulation of digital platforms. The **US government's delineation** of information warfare includes three principal categories: offensive, defensive, and exploitative.

- ❖ **Offensive** endeavors encompass efforts aimed at denying, corrupting, destroying, or exploiting an adversary's information or influencing their perceptions.
- ❖ **Defensive** measures concentrate on protecting oneself and allies from

comparable actions, also recognized as information warfare hardening.

- ❖ **Exploitative tactics** entail utilizing accessible information promptly to bolster decision-making and action cycles, consequently disrupting the adversary's operations (Kovacich & Jones, 2006).

In the context of this research, the focus is on exploring defensive measures, which are perceived as a form of positive information strategy beneficial to both Iran and Pakistan. According to the US Defense Information Systems Agency (DISA), Information Strategy is described as:

"Actions taken to achieve information superiority in support of national military strategy by affecting adversary information and information systems while leveraging and protecting our information and information systems" (High-Technology Crime Investigator's Handbook, 2006)".

Conceptualizing our understanding of strategy is a challenging endeavor. The entrenched tradition of strategic thought, particularly shaped during the Cold War era, complicates any attempt to envision the "future" of strategy in a meaningful manner. Within this tradition, heavily influenced by the neo-realist school of international relations theory, it is deemed inappropriate to consider the future trajectory of strategy. Strategy, much like the broader field of international relations, is perceived as governed by timeless principles and doctrines. While specific factors such as institutions, power dynamics, and technological advancements may evolve, the fundamental essence of the strategy remains constant. The strategic principles articulated

by historical figures like Thucydides, Sun Tzu, Clausewitz, and Frederick the Great are regarded as immutable. These enduring principles of statecraft are viewed as resistant to fundamental change (Williams, 1993).

The concept of strategic information warfare, as outlined by Molander, Riddile, and Wilson (1996), is characterized by several fundamental features. Firstly, it presents a low barrier to entry, unlike traditional weaponry, requiring minimal financial investment and primarily relying on expertise in information systems and network access. Secondly, it blurs traditional boundaries, merging public and private interests and transcending geographic limitations due to the interconnected nature of the information infrastructure. Thirdly, perception management assumes a crucial role, utilizing novel information-based techniques to manipulate perceptions and deceive, challenging governments in garnering support for security endeavors. This underscores the necessity for innovative analysis methods to comprehend the complex vulnerabilities and targets in strategic intelligence. However, the inability to differentiate strategic information warfare attacks from other cyberspace activities poses significant tactical challenges. Additionally, the complexity of forming and sustaining coalitions heightens vulnerabilities to such attacks, offering adversaries disproportionate advantages. These insights underscore the critical importance of understanding and effectively countering strategic information warfare in contemporary security landscapes (Molander, Riddile, & Wilson, 1996).

Figure 1—Strategic Information Warfare

Molander, Figure: R. C., Riddile, A., & Wilson, P. A. (1996). *Strategic Information Warfare: A New Face of War*. Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation

In the twenty-first century, warfare has undergone significant transformation due to unprecedented technological advancements, leading to a progressive evolution in the art of warfighting (Abbasi, 2020). As the costs associated with traditional warfare continue to escalate beyond sustainability, there has been a noticeable shift towards cost-effective and results-oriented strategies aimed at overcoming adversaries. Consequently, various approaches such as information warfare, 4th generation warfare, 5th generation warfare, non-conventional warfare, asymmetric warfare, and cyber warfare have gained prominence in military discourse (Abbasi, 2020). Within this context, the research question arises: How do these emerging forms of warfare impact the security dynamics of nations like Pakistan and Iran, particularly in light of their vulnerabilities to hybrid threats and the need for effective perception management strategies? Like numerous other states, Pakistan grapples with the challenge of strategic information warfare orchestrated by its adversaries. Factors such as ethno-nationalistic concerns, religious radicalization, political instability, and socioeconomic issues contribute to Pakistan's vulnerability to hybrid threats. With the rise of hybrid threats, effective perception management has become increasingly crucial for national security. Given the unparalleled technological advancements in the media domain, Pakistan's

national security interests are becoming increasingly intertwined with implementing effective perception management strategies (Abbasi, 2020). In the context of Pak-Iran relations, information strategy and shaping public narrative have emerged as critical determinants of diplomatic success and regional stability. Enhancing diplomatic stability focuses on promoting consistency, predictability, and reliability in diplomatic interactions between Pakistan and Iran. It involves fostering an environment where diplomatic relations between the two nations are characterized by mutual trust, respect, and cooperation. Enhancing diplomatic stability aims to prevent or mitigate conflicts, misunderstandings, and tensions that may arise in bilateral relations. However, despite recognizing the significance of information strategy in bolstering bilateral ties, there remains a gap in understanding its nuanced application and implications. This research aims to investigate the role of information strategy in shaping public narrative within the Pak-Iran context, exploring its potential to enhance mutual understanding, mitigate conflicts, and foster stronger diplomatic relations between the two nations.

Literature Review

FIRST PHASE

Pak-Iran Relations Historical Background:

Iran and Pakistan are key stakeholders in South-West Asia, sharing contiguous borders that render their bilateral relations strategically significant. Given their geographic proximity, the nature and dynamics of their interactions hold immense

implications for regional peace and stability. The imperative for fostering amicable and cooperative ties between these neighboring nations cannot be overstated (Montazeran & Mumtaz, 2004). Iran holds immense strategic and geographical importance for Pakistan, rooted in their shared boundary along the Goldsmith line stretching approximately 590 miles from Koh-i-Malik Saih to Gwadar Bay in the Arabian Sea. This proximity fosters a deep sense of kinship among the Baloch tribe, driven by linguistic, ethnic, and cultural ties. Geographically, this shared boundary not only facilitates economic collaboration but also significantly influences regional security dynamics, shaping the broader context of Pak-Iran relations.

Balochistan, as a central province within Pakistan, serves as a crucial link in shaping bilateral ties with Iran, acting as a pivotal transit hub connecting the two nations. The frequent interactions between Baloch communities across the border, coupled with engagements between the Hazara community in Quetta and cities like Qum in Iran, underscore the enduring socio-cultural bonds that transcend geopolitical boundaries (Khan, 2012).

Post-Independence Relations:

Pakistan and Iran share a longstanding history of warm and amicable relations. Dating back to the earliest days of Pakistan's independence, Iran was among the first nations to officially recognize Pakistan's sovereignty in August 1947, establishing its diplomatic mission in Karachi that same year. Pakistan reciprocated by appointing its inaugural ambassador to Iran in May 1948. A treaty of friendship between the two nations was formalized on February 19, 1950, affirming principles of good neighborliness and extending most favored nation treatment (Qureshi, 1995). During the Shah's reign, Pakistan and Iran forged a robust alliance, marked by Iran's vital support during critical moments in Pakistan's history. Notably, Iran provided diplomatic and material aid during the 1965 Indo-Pakistani war, with high-level

consultations between President Ayub and the Shah, and a resolute statement from Iran promising full support to Pakistan (Montazeran & Mumtaz, 2004).

The Cold War Era and Regional Cooperation:

This alliance endured changes in Pakistan's leadership, as successive administrations prioritized bilateral ties with Iran for mutual political, and economic interests, and regional stability. In the early 1970s, Iran's substantial military aid played a crucial role in Pakistan's successful containment of a separatist insurgency in Baluchistan, highlighting their deep cooperation (Bokhari, 2003).

Expanding beyond politics and security, the relationship diversified into economic and technical cooperation under the Regional Cooperation for Development (RCD), established by Iran, Pakistan, and Turkey from 1964 to 1979. While RCD's economic impact was modest, it significantly boosted cultural collaboration. Furthermore, RCD paved the way for the formation of the Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO) in 1985, streamlining operations and fostering greater efficiency (Bukhari, 2002).

Strategic Alliances and Boundary Agreements:

During the initial phases, three primary factors were pivotal in shaping the strong bond between Iran and Pakistan. Firstly, their joint membership in the Central Treaty Organization (CENTO) facilitated extensive collaboration. Secondly, an agreement concerning their disputed border was reached, with the establishment of a joint Iran-Pakistan Boundary Commission in 1956 and subsequent border delineation in 1958, mitigating potential conflicts (Chopra, 1967). Thirdly, Iran played a crucial role in mediating peace between Pakistan and Afghanistan amid escalating tensions, following Pakistan's entry into CENTO and Afghanistan's heightened hostility, leading to the re-establishment of diplomatic ties

through direct negotiations facilitated by Iran in 1963 (Montazeran & Mumtaz, 2004).

The 1990s and Divergent Paths:

During the 1990s, the relationship between Pakistan and Iran experienced a notable decline. Several factors contributed to this downward trajectory in their bilateral relations. Firstly, the Afghan factor played a pivotal role, as Pakistan and Iran adopted divergent approaches towards the situation in Afghanistan. Additionally, sectarian tensions within Pakistan exacerbated strains between the two nations. Furthermore, Pakistan's extensive support for the Taliban regime in Afghanistan further solidified Iran and India's natural alliance against the Taliban. This alliance, united in opposition to the Taliban regime, caused concern among Pakistani policymakers. They were particularly perturbed by the growing cooperation between India and Iran, viewing it within the context of Indian efforts to encircle Pakistan. This concern heightened with the establishment of an Indian Consulate, reflecting Pakistan's apprehensions about potential encirclement efforts by its neighbors (Montazeran & Mumtaz, 2004).

Post 9/11 and Economic Collaboration:

In the historical context, Pak-Iran relations have seen significant strides forward since November 2001 (Montazeran & Mumtaz, 2004). Notably, in 2022, recent trade statistics from the Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC) indicate that Iran's exports to Pakistan totaled \$762 million. Key exports included petroleum gas (\$478 million), electricity (\$48.5 million), and petroleum coke (\$43.6 million). Notably, this trade partnership has been steadily growing since 2001, with Iran's exports to Pakistan showing consistent annual increases. Over the past 25 years, these exports have seen significant expansion, rising from \$29.5 million in 1997 to \$762 million in 2022, reflecting the strengthening economic ties between the two nations.

Integration of Historical Perspectives:

Understanding the historical context illuminates the factors that have shaped the bilateral relationship between Pakistan and Iran, from cooperative endeavors to periods of tension and discord. This historical backdrop serves as a valuable lens through which to analyze the dynamics of public diplomacy and strategic culture between the two nations. By examining past interactions, policy decisions, and socio-political developments, stakeholders can gain a deeper understanding of the underlying drivers and challenges in fostering mutual understanding, cooperation, and stability. Integrating historical perspectives into discussions on public diplomacy and strategic culture is essential for crafting informed strategies and forging resilient partnerships in the contemporary geopolitical landscape. The integration of historical perspectives is crucial in understanding the complexities of Pak-Iran relations. The historical narrative of these relations provides insights into the evolving nature of their diplomatic, economic, and security interactions.

For instance, the early years of Pakistan's independence saw a robust and supportive relationship with Iran, marked by Iran's early recognition of Pakistan and subsequent diplomatic engagements (Qureshi, 1995). This period laid the foundation for a relationship based on mutual respect and cooperation. During the Shah's regime, Iran's substantial military and economic support to Pakistan during critical moments, such as the Indo-Pakistani wars, exemplified the strategic alliance between the two nations (Montazeran & Mumtaz, 2004).

This period of close cooperation underscores the importance of historical alliances in shaping current diplomatic strategies. The strategic culture during this era was heavily influenced by shared security concerns and the mutual goal of regional stability. The transition from the Shah's regime to the Islamic Republic brought significant changes in Iran's foreign policy, impacting its relations with Pakistan. The Iranian Revolution

introduced a new dimension to the bilateral relationship, characterized by ideological shifts and sectarian dynamics.

Pakistan's predominantly Sunni population and Iran's Shia regime introduced complexities that continue to influence their diplomatic interactions today (Khan, 2012). Understanding these ideological and sectarian influences is essential for developing effective public diplomacy strategies that address these underlying tensions. The establishment of the Regional Cooperation for Development (RCD) and later the Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO) highlighted the economic dimensions of Pak-Iran relations. These initiatives aimed at enhancing economic collaboration and cultural exchange, reflect the importance of economic interdependence in fostering diplomatic ties (Bukhari, 2002). The historical success and challenges of these organizations provide valuable lessons for current economic and technical cooperation initiatives between the two nations. The geopolitical shifts of the 1990s, particularly the divergent approaches to the Afghan conflict and the rise of the Taliban, marked a period of strain in Pak-Iran relations.

Pakistan's support for the Taliban contrasted with Iran's opposition, leading to tensions that were further exacerbated by sectarian divides within Pakistan (Montazeran & Mumtaz, 2004). These historical tensions underscore the need for nuanced information strategies that can bridge ideological divides and promote mutual understanding. Post-9/11 developments brought new dimensions to Pak-Iran relations, with both countries facing common challenges such as terrorism and regional instability. The increase in economic ties, as evidenced by rising trade volumes, indicates a mutual recognition of the benefits of economic cooperation (OEC, 2022). This economic interdependence provides a platform for enhancing diplomatic relations through shared economic interests. Incorporating historical perspectives into the analysis of public diplomacy and strategic culture offers a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing Pak-Iran relations.

Historical events, such as the support during wars, economic cooperation through RCD and ECO, and the ideological shifts post-Iranian Revolution, highlight the multifaceted nature of their relationship.

By recognizing and addressing these historical influences, policymakers can develop more effective strategies that leverage historical alliances, address ideological divides, and promote long-term cooperation. Furthermore, the historical analysis reveals the critical role of strategic culture in shaping information strategies. The interplay between Pakistan's and Iran's strategic cultures, influenced by their historical experiences, affects how they perceive and respond to regional threats and opportunities. For example, Pakistan's strategic culture, shaped by its historical conflict with India and its alliances with Western powers, emphasizes military strength and strategic alliances (Ziring, 1997). In contrast, Iran's strategic culture, informed by its revolutionary ideology and historical resistance to Western influence, focuses on self-reliance and regional influence (Haghshenass, 2013). By integrating these historical perspectives into contemporary policy analysis, stakeholders can better understand the underlying motivations and constraints shaping Pak-Iran relations. This historical context provides a framework for developing public diplomacy initiatives that resonate with both nations' strategic cultures, fostering a more stable and cooperative regional environment.

SECOND PHASE

Strategic Culture Synergy: Pak-Iran Information Strategy:

Strategic culture refers to the shared beliefs, values, and historical experiences of the ruling elite within a country, which shape their understanding of security issues and guide their responses. It acts as a lens through which policymakers view the external security landscape, interpret information, and make decisions. This collective mindset influences how policymakers perceive threats,

assess available information, and determine appropriate policy options in various situations (Rizvi, H.-A. 2002). Moreover, strategic culture doesn't exist in isolation; it intersects with information strategy, becoming a pivotal factor in how nations communicate and engage with the world. By understanding their strategic culture, countries can tailor their information strategies to effectively convey their perceptions of regional threats, attitudes towards military force, and strategies for dealing with adversaries. Pakistan's strategic culture, influenced by its history of conflict with neighboring India and its geostrategic position in South Asia, emphasizes the importance of military strength and strategic alliances for safeguarding national security (Ziring, 1997).

Similarly, Iran's strategic culture is informed by its historical grievances with Western powers and its aspirations for regional influence, leading to a focus on self-reliance and resistance against external pressures (Haghshenass, 2013). In the realm of Pak-Iran's strategic culture, Dr. S.M. Burke underscores Pakistan's profound affinity for Iran, attributing it to Iran's status as the progenitor of Pakistani culture and Persian as the precursor to Urdu, our national language (Burke, 1973). Moreover, the shared border region inhabited by the Baloch tribe further solidifies this cultural bond, as linguistic, ethnic, and traditional similarities abound (Abidi, A.H.H., August 1977). The interaction between Baloch communities on both sides of the border primarily revolves around socio-cultural and economic exchanges. While the border does impose some limitations on such interactions, it remains relatively permeable compared to other international borders connected to Iran.

The presence of custom posts and check posts does impose scrutiny on travelers, but regular and irregular entry points, notably near Taftan and Panjgur, facilitate movement between the two regions (Dawn, Karachi, November 12, 2005). Notably, five border districts predominantly inhabited by Baloch and Barhvi populations serve as focal points for

cross-border activities: Panjgur, Chagai, Wasuk, Turbat, and Gwader. While Kharan was previously a significant district bordering Iran, border demarcation resulting from the formation of new districts has altered its status (Dawn, Karachi, November 12, 2005). The Baloch residing on either side of the border often hold dual nationality, facilitating frequent border crossings for various purposes, including visiting relatives, socializing with friends, cultural engagements, seeking employment, and conducting trade and business activities. Inter-marriages are common among the Baloch, facilitated by family bonds and further opportunities for interaction across the border (Marri, 1974).

The Iranian Cultural Center in Quetta plays a pivotal role in promoting and strengthening cultural relations between the provinces of the two countries. Through conferences, seminars, workshops, and social gatherings, the center fosters dialogue and exchange among scholars, intellectuals, students, and individuals from various walks of life (Marri, 1974). Additionally, the center offers courses in Pakistani language and calligraphy, reflecting Iran's commitment to cultural diplomacy and people-to-people exchanges (Marri, 1974). These multifaceted interactions underscore the resilience of cultural bonds between Pakistan and Iran, transcending geopolitical boundaries and fostering mutual understanding and cooperation. These interactions blur the distinction between the two regions, fostering a sense of familiarity and belonging regardless of the border's presence.

Analyzing the Interplay of Pak-Iran Relations and Militant Organizations:

The recent series of airstrikes between Pakistan and Iran, occurring on January 16, 2024, serves as a poignant illustration of the profound influence of strategic culture on information strategy and public perception. Iran's unexpected missile strikes into Pakistan's Baluchistan province, purportedly targeting alleged strongholds of the anti-Iran insurgent group Jaish al-Adl, were met with

swift retaliation from Pakistan. This retaliatory action, involving strikes into Iran's Sistan- Baluchistan province, aimed to target hideouts of anti-Pakistan ethno-nationalist insurgents (Mir, 2024). This exchange highlights the intricate interplay between strategic imperatives, cultural identities, and information dissemination strategies. Both nations' actions were not merely reactive measures but calculated responses shaped by historical, religious, and geopolitical factors inherent in their strategic cultures. For Pakistan, the imperative to assert sovereignty and deter threats to national security guided its defensive information strategy in framing the airstrikes as necessary measures to safeguard its borders.

Conversely, Iran's strikes underscored its commitment to combat perceived threats and project strength, leveraging information strategy to justify its actions domestically and internationally (Mir, 2024). Moreover, the presence of militant organizations such as Jundallah further complicates the strategic landscape and influences information strategy dynamics. Jundallah's activities, aimed at advocating for Sunni Muslim rights in Iran, not only exacerbate regional tensions but also shape public perception and decision-making processes. The portrayal of these events through the lens of strategic culture informs defensive information strategies, enabling policymakers to navigate complex narratives, manage public opinion, and project a unified stance against external threats. Furthermore, understanding the underlying motivations and cultural contexts provides decision-makers with valuable insights into crafting effective communication strategies to mitigate risks, build trust, and foster regional stability (Wiig, 2009).

Examining these examples through the lens of strategic culture provides valuable insights into the intricate interplay between historical legacies, religious identities, and geopolitical factors that influence Pakistan and Iran's behavior in security and diplomacy. Strategic culture serves as a foundational framework shaping the perceptions and motivations of

decision-makers in both nations, guiding their actions and responses in times of conflict and cooperation. This understanding highlights the importance of adopting nuanced approaches to managing tensions and promoting mutual understanding in the Pak-Iran relationship. Furthermore, it underscores the critical role of information strategy in shaping public perception and guiding defensive measures. By aligning communication efforts with the cultural values and strategic imperatives of each nation, policymakers can effectively navigate complex narratives, manage public opinion, and bolster regional stability.

Public Diplomacy-Pak Iran Information Strategy:

The soft power of a nation relies primarily on three key resources: its culture, political values, and foreign policies. Culture encompasses the practices that give significance to a society, ranging from high culture like literature and art to popular culture focused on mass entertainment. Efforts to shape favorable perceptions of one's nation are not novel, yet the dynamics of projecting soft power have evolved significantly in recent years. With close to half of the world's countries now embracing democracy, the traditional Cold War paradigm for public diplomacy has lost some of its relevance. While the imperative to disseminate accurate information remains critical in nations with tightly controlled media environments like Burma or Syria, there is now a growing need to cultivate positive public opinion in countries such as Mexico and Turkey, where parliamentary influence holds sway (Nye, 2008). For instance, during attempts to garner international support for the Iraq war, including securing Mexico's vote in the UN or obtaining Turkey's approval for troop deployment, the waning soft power of the United States hindered rather than facilitated its objectives (Nye, 2004).

The importance of shaping public opinion is accentuated in post-authoritarian contexts,

where public sentiment can significantly influence the decisions of newly empowered parliaments and leaders. Diplomatic efforts aimed at public opinion are thus increasingly pivotal, alongside traditional channels of classified diplomatic communications among leaders. The adage “information is power” holds particular resonance in an era where a larger segment of the global population has access to information (Dizard, 2004). Gone are the days when diplomatic envoys traversed remote regions to convey messages through reel-to-reel movies. Technological advancements have drastically reduced the cost of processing and transmitting information, leading to an information explosion and, paradoxically, attention scarcity (Nye, 2011). In an age of information abundance, individuals are inundated with data, making it increasingly challenging to discern what warrants their attention.

In the context of Pakistan-Iran relations, the significance of public diplomacy cannot be overstated, particularly in light of Nye's assertion that public opinion holds considerable sway over the actions of stakeholders (Nye, 2008). As neighboring countries, Pakistan and Iran stand to benefit from ensuring that their populations are aligned with government policies and that public perception fosters support for bilateral cooperation. In an era where attention has become a scarce resource amid the deluge of information, the ability to capture and maintain credibility emerges as a crucial aspect of wielding soft power (Nye, 2004). Governments, including those of Pakistan and Iran, find themselves engaged in a competitive struggle to shape narratives and influence public opinion, both domestically and internationally.

Pak-Iran Relations: Exploring Public Policy Dimensions:

Public diplomacy involves three crucial dimensions that significantly influence international relations, including the dynamic between Pakistan and Iran (Nye, 2008). Firstly, Continuous and effective

communication, both domestically and internationally, is crucial for providing context to policy decisions and maintaining commitment to bilateral relationships (Leonard, 2002). While prioritizing communication with domestic media is common, engaging with foreign outlets, particularly during crises, is equally vital (Nye, 2008). In the realm of Pakistan-Iran relations, the media plays a pivotal role in disseminating and promoting the bilateral message, rallying public participation and enthusiasm to nurture the relationship (Zehra, N. 2003). This underscores the significance of the first dimension of public diplomacy, “daily communications” in which the rationale behind domestic and foreign policy decisions is elucidated. While government officials typically prioritize communication with the domestic press, it is imperative to recognize the pivotal role of engaging with foreign media outlets, particularly in the initial stages of public diplomacy (Nye, 2008). Secondly, strategic communication entails developing simple themes similar to political or advertising campaigns to reinforce central messages or advance specific policies (Nye, 2008). Pakistan's historical efforts to strengthen its relationship with Iran underscore the crucial role of strategic communication in advancing specific policies. The establishment of institutions like the Pakistan-Iran Joint Commission on Communications highlights the significance of strategic communication channels between the two nations (Zehra, N. 2003). This aligns with the second dimension of public diplomacy, which involves strategic communication. Strategic communication is essential not only for promoting central messages or advancing government policies but also for exerting pressure on other countries to avoid mistakes or prevent the escalation of situations.

The third dimension of public diplomacy focuses on nurturing lasting relationships with key individuals through scholarships, exchanges, and training programs. These interactions not only foster mutual

understanding but also lay the groundwork for long-term partnerships and cooperation. For instance, American cultural and academic exchanges have been instrumental in educating world leaders, fostering enduring friendships, and enhancing diplomatic ties (Nye, 2008). In the sphere of Pakistan-Iran relations, the implementation of exchange programs between diverse universities and research institutions could facilitate the provision of scholarships for higher education in each other's academic institutions (Montazeran, A., & Mumtaz, K. (2004).

These endeavors not only foster mutual comprehension but also establish the groundwork for enduring partnerships and collaboration. This aligns with the third dimension of public diplomacy, which emphasizes the cultivation of enduring connections with influential individuals over extended periods. Such connections are nurtured through a variety of channels including scholarships, exchanges, training sessions, seminars, conferences, and access to media platforms. Over time, these interactions have played a pivotal role in educating and shaping the perspectives of global leaders like Anwar Sadat, Helmut Schmidt, and Margaret Thatcher, as evidenced by their participation in American cultural and academic exchanges (Nye, 2008). All three dimensions of public diplomacy is pivotal in crafting a positive image of a nation and influencing its ability to achieve its objectives. However, effective public diplomacy transcends mere promotion; it hinges on policies perceived as genuine and beneficial, as opposed to narrowly self-serving or arrogant. While enduring friendships may engender some leniency or forgiveness, insincerity or hubris can impede the cultivation of soft power (Nye, 2008).

Interpreting Public Diplomacy:

Effective public diplomacy operates as a reciprocal process, involving attentive listening alongside strategic communication. Understanding the perspectives and shared values of others is essential. Exchanges, rather than unilateral broadcasting, often yield

greater efficacy. Soft power inherently aims at aligning others' objectives with one's own, demanding an understanding of how messages resonate and the ability to adapt them accordingly. Crucially, comprehending the target audience is paramount. However, research on foreign public opinion remains inadequately funded. Merely preaching at foreigners is ineffective; political leaders often oversimplify the challenge, assuming that others lack information. Yet, all information is filtered through cultural lenses, and declarative statements are seldom interpreted as intended (Nye, 2008). In the context of Pakistan-Iran relations, overlooking the deep cultural ties between Balochistan and Sistan undermines efforts to shape public perception effectively.

To foster mutual understanding, leaders must empathize with the perspectives of Balochistan- Sistan residents, acknowledging the significance of shared cultural bonds and religious heritage. Addressing their needs and providing development opportunities are essential steps toward fostering unity and cooperation. In the realm of effective public diplomacy, active listening is as crucial as articulating messages. Understanding the perspectives and values of others is pivotal rendering exchanges more impactful than one-sided broadcasting. Soft power hinges on aligning others' interests with one's own, necessitating an understanding of how messages are perceived and adapting them accordingly. Yet, research on foreign public opinion remains underfunded, underscoring the importance of comprehending cultural filters through which information is received. Actions and symbols that demonstrate intentions often surpass declarative statements in influence. For instance, initiatives such as increasing development assistance or addressing HIV/AIDS, initially promising under the Bush administration, lost significance amid the Iraq conflict.

Conversely, providing Tsunami relief to Indonesia in 2004 helped mitigate the decline in America's favorability following the Iraq war (Nye, 2008). While broadcasting remains integral to public diplomacy, its efficacy can

be augmented by targeted communication via the Internet. Despite primarily reaching elites due to economic constraints, the Internet's affordability and adaptability enable tailored messaging to specific demographics and circumvention of government censorship. Moreover, the Internet facilitates interactive exchanges, complementing face-to-face communication (Nye, 2008). However, ensuring alignment between words and actions is paramount in public diplomacy. Domestic resonance may not necessarily translate to international impact. For instance, while President Bush's reference to an "axis of evil" was well-received domestically, it elicited negative reactions abroad. Similarly, declaring a "war on terrorism" galvanized domestic support but complicated cooperative efforts against terrorism abroad, contributing to perceptions of unilateralism (Nye, 2007).

Actions demonstrating mutual cooperation and understanding, particularly in vital areas such as economic collaboration and cultural exchange, possess significant potential to positively influence the perceptions of both Iranians and Balochi's in favor of Pakistan. These initiatives not only bolster bilateral relations but also foster a sense of trust and goodwill between the two nations. By actively engaging in joint ventures, promoting people-to-people interactions, and facilitating cross-border initiatives, Pakistan can effectively convey its commitment to strengthening ties with Iran and addressing shared challenges collaboratively. Even when governmental policies and communication strategies align, harnessing soft power resources in the digital era presents formidable challenges. Government-led communications represent only a fraction of the extensive information exchanges shaping global perceptions. Influential factors like Hollywood productions or activities of non-governmental entities often operate independently, influencing perceptions beyond government control.

While some advocate for a laissez-faire approach, relying solely on market-driven media outlets like CNN or Fox News risks oversimplifying a country's cultural

representation and reinforcing stereotypes (Nye, 2008). In today's postmodern landscape, where public skepticism towards governmental authority is prevalent, governments are often met with mistrust. Therefore, it is prudent for governments to maintain a low profile and collaborate with trusted private actors. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), enjoying higher levels of public trust, serve as valuable conduits for communication despite their independent nature (Nye, 2008). Similarly, in the realm of Pak-Iran relations, media and social media platforms play a pivotal role in shaping public perception. Pakistani media outlets can draw from the strategies employed by influential global entities like Hollywood or CNN, emphasizing themes of mutual cooperation and shared values between the two nations. Through sustained engagement and cultural initiatives, Pakistan can gradually influence perceptions within Iran and among the Balochi community. While the impacts may not be immediate, these efforts align with Joseph Nye's notion that enduring relationships often yield greater diplomatic dividends than short-term approaches.

Methodology

Research Design:

This study employs a qualitative research design to explore the impact of defensive information strategies on Pak-Iran relations. Given the complex and nuanced nature of information warfare and its implications for diplomatic stability, a qualitative approach allows for an in-depth understanding of the phenomena. The research involves structured interviews and surveys with key stakeholders from various professional fields, including military officers, foreign office officials, academics, and individuals from Iran.

Data Collection Method:

The data for this research was collected through a series of structured interviews and surveys, targeting key individuals from various professional fields to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the impact of

strategic culture and information strategies in Pak-Iran relations. The respondents were carefully selected to provide diverse perspectives, encompassing military officers, foreign office officials, academics, and individuals from Iran.

Data Collection Summary:

Table: Interview Participants

Field	Number of Interviewees
Military Officers	5
Foreign Office	5
Academia	5
Iranian Participants	5
Total	20

The data collection involved interviewing five individuals from each of the following fields: military, foreign office, academia, and Iranian participants. The structured interviews were designed to elicit detailed responses on the role of information strategies and strategic culture in shaping public perceptions and diplomatic relations.

The structured and systematic approach to data collection ensured that the research captured a wide range of perspectives. The involvement of senior military officers, foreign office officials, academics, and Iranian participants provided a comprehensive and balanced understanding of the complex dynamics at play in Pak-Iran relations. This collaborative effort highlights the importance of cross-disciplinary cross-border cooperation in conducting meaningful and impactful research.

comprehensive understanding of the impact and effectiveness of these strategies

Analysis and Discussion

Analysis:

The collected data was analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring themes and patterns related to the research questions. The analysis focused on:

The Role of Information Warfare:

How defensive information strategies influence public narratives and their implications for diplomatic success and regional stability.

The analysis of the interview data reveals diverse perspectives on how information strategies influence the public narrative concerning Pak-Iran relations. This section synthesizes insights from various respondents, including army officers, foreign office officials, and academics, providing a

1. Army Officers Analysis

The responses from army officers underscore the pivotal role of information strategies in enhancing the understanding of policy decisions among both the elite and the general public. These strategies are seen as crucial tools for elucidating complex policy issues, thus facilitating a more informed public discourse. Some officers specifically highlighted the historical context, noting that Pakistan and Iran's policies were aligned until the 1970s. However, the Iranian Revolution marked a significant shift in Iran's alliance from the US to Russia, which, coupled with sectarian differences (predominantly Sunni Pakistan versus Shia Iran), has complicated the alignment of public opinion between the two nations. One officer emphasized that over 20% of Pakistan's population is Shia, and this demographic is highly sensitive about their religious beliefs. This sensitivity influences their opinions about Iran, often leading to a more favorable view of Iranian policies and culture.

Iran has strategically leveraged this sensitivity by attempting to sway the Pakistani Shia population through religious and cultural initiatives, such as the establishment of "Khana e Farhang" (houses of culture). These

initiatives are designed to foster a cultural and religious connection, thereby influencing public perception. Moreover, misconceptions about Persian civilization add another layer of complexity to the public narrative. Many Pakistanis mistakenly attribute the entirety of Persian civilization to modern Iran, overlooking the historical contributions of other regions. This misconception further complicates the public's understanding and perception of Iran. Other officers observed that information strategies positively influence public opinion more broadly. They noted that these strategies not only improve the public's understanding of policy decisions but also positively shape public opinion. This positive influence is reflected in a more favorable view of diplomatic efforts and policy measures, suggesting that well-crafted information strategies can effectively foster public support for diplomatic initiatives.

2. Foreign Office Officials Analysis

Foreign office officials largely concur that information strategies significantly impact public understanding and opinion. Some noted that these strategies help clarify complex policy decisions, making them accessible to the general public and fostering a supportive environment for diplomatic initiatives. They emphasized that effectively communicating the intentions and benefits of policy measures builds public trust and consensus, which is essential for successful bilateral relations. Another official underscored that shaping public perceptions favorably through information strategies bolsters support for diplomatic initiatives, enhancing their legitimacy and effectiveness. However, one official warned that while these strategies clarify policy decisions, they can also create

misconceptions if not managed properly, highlighting the need for accurate dissemination. Another official explained that biased or incomplete information could lead to public misconceptions, emphasizing the importance of accuracy and comprehensiveness in information strategy. Yet another reiterated the positive influence of effective information strategies, which foster a supportive environment for diplomatic efforts and enhance the overall perception of national policies.

3. Academia Analysis

Academics provide a nuanced and critical analysis of the impact of information strategies on public narratives in Pak-Iran relations. The complexity of these strategies is evident in their varied impact; while they can enhance the understanding of policy decisions, they also have the potential to create misconceptions and, at times, may have no noticeable impact at all. This variability underscores the multifaceted nature of information dissemination and reception within different segments of the population. Information strategies frequently fail to produce a noticeable impact, suggesting a potential gap in their effectiveness. This perspective points to a disconnect between the intended outcomes of these strategies and their actual influence on public perception, highlighting the challenges inherent in crafting messages that resonate broadly and accurately with diverse audiences. In improving policy understanding, information strategies tend to be more effective among the elite than among the general public. The limited impact on the general populace can be attributed to deep-seated sectarian differences between Shia-majority Iran and Sunni-majority Pakistan.

Aspect of Influence	Percentage (%)
Improves understanding of policy decisions (A)	53.33
Influences public opinion positively (B)	46.67
Creates misconceptions or misunderstandings (C)	26.67
No noticeable impact (D)	13.33
Building trust and mutual understanding	40.00
By fostering mutual understanding and trust	6.67
By promoting economic cooperation and trade agreements	6.67
Facilitating cultural and educational exchanges	20.00
Promoting economic cooperation and trade	26.67
Disseminating targeted propaganda through social and traditional media	60.00
Using diplomatic channels to negotiate peace	20.00

These sectarian divides create substantial barriers to a cohesive public narrative, as the cultural and religious contexts significantly influence how information is perceived and internalized. The sectarian context complicates the information landscape, making it difficult for a single narrative to take hold across both nations. The entrenched sectarian identities mean that information strategies need to be particularly sensitive and tailored to address these deep-rooted differences. The academic perspective underscores the necessity for a more sophisticated and contextually aware approach to information dissemination, one that recognizes and navigates the complex interplay of sectarian, cultural, and political factors in shaping public opinion. In sum, the academic viewpoints collectively highlight that while information strategies can be powerful tools for shaping public narratives, their effectiveness is highly contingent on the sociopolitical and sectarian context. To optimize these strategies, it is crucial to address the underlying barriers and tailor communication efforts to the specific nuances of the target audiences.

Discussion:

The discussion emphasizes how crucial defensive information tactics are in forming public perceptions and affecting ties between Pakistan and Iran. The historical and sectarian dynamics are emphasized by army officials, who also point out how Iran strategically uses cultural endeavors

to influence Pakistan's Shia majority and dispel myths about Persian civilization. To promote public trust and support for diplomatic endeavors, foreign office officials emphasize the significance of accessibility, accuracy, and clarity in the distribution of information while cautioning against the dangers of false information. Scholars offer a nuanced viewpoint, highlighting the need for context-sensitive and customized techniques by pointing out that these tactics have little effect on the broader public because of ingrained cultural and sectarian divides. All things considered, the results show that although information tactics can promote comprehension and assistance, their success depends on removing geopolitical and sectarian obstacles and developing focused narratives that appeal to a range of audiences.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between information strategies, and public diplomacy, in Pak-Iran relations. By addressing the identified gaps and providing practical recommendations, the study offers valuable guidance for policymakers seeking to enhance diplomatic stability and foster stronger bilateral ties. Through a combination of academic analysis and empirical data, this scholarly work underscores the critical importance of aligning information strategies with national policies and cultural contexts to promote mutual understanding and long-term diplomatic cooperation.

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